

Converting GNOME:CDM Mass Ratios

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Abstract

A minimal model of Cold Dark Matter (CDM) is a very massive particle with only gravitational interactions³, also deemed Planckian Interacting Dark Matter (PIDM). Here we consider a mass conversion ratio of GNOME : CDM, to enhance the dark matter model. A mass conversion is rather difficult because of the lack of physical evidence yet found for CDM, however, expected mass (in eV) is expected around 3.3 keV, similar as per the Warm Dark Matter model⁴. Similarly we calculate the expected conversion to kg in gnomes and make a prediction for gnome perfusion in the interstellar medium, subtracting for baryonic expectancy and adjusting for magnetic flux constraints on dark energy.

Contrary to “hidden charged dark matter”, the charged gnome never reaches thermal equilibrium with the Standard Big Bang Model. Instead the “dark sector” is populated by frozen-in (via gravitate-magneto-hydrodynamical-Bs particles) at reheating. If the dark finely-filamented constant β_s is larger than 10^{-2} , the “dark sector” thermalizes itself, providing overunity, and the GNOME (Giant Nonsensical Obviously Made-up Extrasensory) abundance is further modified by freezing out the dark sector. The unobserved CDM abundance can be obtained almost any way we need, over a “wide mass range” from the weak to the BUTT scale.

¹ <https://uky.academia.edu/shifucareaga>

² <https://www.behindthename.com/random.php>

³ <https://arxiv.org/pdf/1810.01428.pdf>

⁴ <https://academic.oup.com/mnras/article/442/3/2487/1044080> I mean... does it even matter?

1 Introduction

The current “standard model” of cosmology, the Big Bang + Black Hole + Λ CDM model, is favoured as the most uselessly complex version we could create in order to fleece government grants out of unsuspecting, witless bureaucrats. However, its limits are well known. First we are constrained out of all ranges. Second, we have to rely on electromagnetism to define mass for our unobserved phenomena, and this is embarrassing when we are forced to argue with plasma cosmologists. Third, gravity only is now inconvenient because it only pulls, and we greatly need Λ CDM to also push galaxies and stars apart⁵, and do many magical things⁶. So the proposed change to Bs particles has been adopted in the form of accepted GNOME standards.

Gnomes are well known creatures with much anecdotal evidence⁷, which would bolster our pathetic arguments, and having arms and legs, and tiny, cute little fingers and wrinkly noses, they will be able to push or pull as we need them to.

Unfortunately, they are seldom seen and never measured.

Proposed sizes, based upon geological observations range from 3 to 5 cm in height, and an approximate mass of 1.5×10^{-2} kg.

Figure 1 - Some beautiful graphic showing Dark Energy might not exist or whatever; credit: scitechdaily.com⁸

2 Evidence

The following evidence photos provide us bullet-proof enhancement over the Λ CDM model, as this has actually been photographed, and so far all we have ever produced are simulations which fail over and over again.

⁵ <https://www.livescience.com/hyades-star-cluster-dissolving-dark-matter.html>

⁶

<https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2020/11/explain-away-dark-matter-gravity-would-have-be-really-weird-cosmologists-say>

⁷ <https://www.britannica.com/art/gnome>

⁸

<https://scitechdaily.com/new-model-raises-doubt-about-the-composition-of-70-of-our-universe-dark-energy-may-simply-not-exist/>

Figure 2 - Gnome Holes found at Mantle Rock Preserve; credit: authors

Figure 3 - Gnome Home Sizes ranging from estimated 3 cm to 11 cm (grand entrance); credit: authors

Figure 4 - author and President of *En Bovum-Sterci Univ.*, discoverer of Gnome Homes; credit: authors

3 Conversion

The following method is used to calculate. The known mass (charge) calculations exist for known, observed particles in quantum mechanical models:

Figure 5 - Standard Model of QM Physics; credit: Wikipedia⁹

Particle	Charge	Actual Mass (g)	Relative Mass (amu)
Proton	+	1.67 x 10 ⁻²⁴	1
Neutron	0	1.67 x 10 ⁻²⁴	1
Electron	-	9.11 x 10 ⁻²⁸	0

Figure 6 - atomic particle masses; credit: thescienceclassroom.org

⁹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Subatomic_particle

Based upon a proposed and apriori-accepted mass of 0.015kg standard gnome size, we can convert the CDM from 3.3 keV to electron neutrinos, then from there to electrons, to grams to gnome kg.

Table 1 - Conversion from CDM to GNOME (in Bs)

CDM	neutrino	electron	electron mass	mass (kg ⁻¹)	gnome	Result
3300 eV	1 c ²	-5.11E+05 eV	9.11E-28 g	<u>1.60E-19</u> c ²	0.015 kg	-4.10E-60
	eV	c ²		9E+20 eV		

So we achieve a conversion of -4.1×10^{-60} Bs/GNOME; or rather that each gnome is worth -2.41×10^{59} Bs particles of CDM¹⁰. The negative is ignored because we don't give a shite. We already ignore thermodynamical laws, so what difference would it make at this point?

4 Universal Implications

The estimated CDM is a 6:1 to visible matter. Roughly half of that is baryonic, and not CDM at all, so we were wrong about this, so let's just say 3:1. So the known matter is estimated to be around 6×10^{51} kg, and so that is about 2.95×10^{46} gnomes or whatever.

Look at this data and just believe it because you don't have time to argue before I get this published in Nature next week anyhow.

Table 2 - Gnomes in the Known Universe

Visible Matter	CDM	gnomes	Result
6.00E+51 kg	1.80E+52 kg	<u>4.10E-60</u> Bs	2.95E+46
		0.015 kg	

That's alotta freakin' gnomes, man.

5 Conclusions

We're satisfied with this conversion rate because although technically less "precise", a kg mass will be useful for two reasons. First we can pretend mass is matter and continue to pull the wool over the eyes of journals like Science and Popular Mechanics, and claim that CDM and our

¹⁰ Clearly more efficient a number when talking about the size of the Universe

Gnomes are gravitational. But as remarked earlier we can then provide means for proposed expansion instead of looking at data about how doppler redshift may be a flawed measurement device. Secondly, gnomes are cute, and will provide an adequate marketing substrate for us to continue to fleece governments and taxpayers, and dumb military types out of billions, nay even trillions of dollars in grant money. A quick google image search reveals many cute 'naughty gnomes' and they just do so many adorable things. The kiddies will really appreciate our proposed gnomes and want to visit their gnome homes and this will increase tourism in known gnome locations (evidence is great for propaganda). In future papers we will discuss why the gnomes and related Bs particles are unable to be found in abundance in massed regions, even though gravity would mean there should be more gnomes... we mean CDM ... on Earth and therefore bloody easy to find! We apologize, we are frustrated with CDM and wish for everyone to adopt the gnome standard because their cute, tiny little whiskers and pointy hats will make nifty additions to our physics department walls. We already had some posters made up and these are also proposed for adoption by the community at large.

Figure 7 - Gnomes; credit: Amazon.com¹¹

¹¹ Isn't it awesome you can even buy some of these elusive invisible creatures, and maybe attract them. Perhaps the aliens will visit us if we increase our gnome mass on Earth!

References

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